

Best Practice Document

Best Practice for the Collection, Processing and Storage of Human Samples

Part 3: Collecting Blood Samples (Whole Blood, Plasma, Serum)

Annex 2.3 to AD4.1

WP 4 – T4.1

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Authors and Acknowledgements

Lead authors

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Contributions for this revised best practice version for PARC WP4 General Survey were received from:

Anna Laura Iamiceli (ISS, Italy), Christina Hartmann (EAA, Austria), Alba Jimeno-Romero (UPV/ EHU, Spain), Marta Esteban (ISCIII, Spain), Janja Snoj Tratnik (JSI, Slovenia), Darja Mazej (JSI, Slovenia), Zanna Martinsone (RSU, Latvia), Svetlana Lakisa (RSU, Latvia), Andrea Krsková (SZU-CZ, Czech Republic), Vladimíra Puklová (SZU-CZ, Czech Republic), Rosa Lange (UBA, Germany), Maria Torres Toda (LNS, Luxembourg), Margaux Riou (SpF, France) and Léa Lefebvre (SpF, France).

Acronyms

CDC	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
DBS	Dried Blood Spots
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HBM4EU	European Human Biomonitoring Initiative
ID	Identifier
LOQ	Limit of Quantification
PARC	European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals
QA	Quality assurance
QC	Quality control
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
VAMS	Volumetric Absorptive MicroSampling
WHO	World Health Organization

1. Introduction

This part of the “Best Practice for the Collection, Processing and Storage of Human Samples” provides detailed instructions for the collection of blood samples (including whole blood and serum) to be used in PARC. Please read carefully “PART 1 – General instructions” of this SOP before starting the collection of human samples – especially the following chapters:

- Precautions in the pre-analytical phase
- Preparations for sampling including pre-treatment of vessels and cryovials
- Field blanks
- Sample conservation, storage & shipment

General remark:

As highlighted in the WHO Guidelines on Drawing Blood, during phlebotomy procedures, the greatest concern is the safety of health workers and blood donors. Therefore, guidance for staff on best practice is critical including relevant vaccination. Training on, and adherence to general guidelines is mandatory to substantially reduce the risks to both blood donors and staff, and will improve blood collection for laboratory tests and from blood donors [1]. For this reason please carefully read the [WHO Guideline on Drawing Blood](#) and the Directive 2010/32/EU to create the safest possible working environment and to avoid needle-stick injuries.

General recommendations for the collection of human samples can be found in CDC (2018) [2].

2. Sampling

Collection and processing of the blood samples according to the PARC specifications is a very important step. If samples are not correctly collected and processed, the analytical results may not be precise or valid.

Detailed information about the timeframe, sample size, target groups, pre-defined criteria, biological matrices, etc. is given in document [PARC General Survey Design](#) (WP4, Task 4.1, Activity 4.1.1, Subactivity, 4.1.1.2 PARC Aligned Studies).

According to the PARC General Survey Design blood samples from following age groups are expected to be collected in each study:

Target Group	Biological Material	Sample type to be collected
Teenagers 12 - 17 years	Blood	Whole blood and serum (plasma)
Adults 18 - 39 years	Blood	Whole blood and serum (plasma)
Children 6 - 11 years (only optional)	Blood	Whole blood and serum (plasma)

The inclusion of further matrices (e.g., dried blood spots (DBS), volumetric absorptive microsampling (VAMS)) is still in discussion.

Best practice:

In studies where multiple aliquots are required for different analyses, a **protocol** should specify the exact procedure including the needed volume and the order in which the aliquots should be collected. This protocol should also specify **analytical priority** in case the volume of the sample is not sufficient for all planned analyses.

2.1. Samples to be collected

The number and type of blood collection tubes depends on different aspects among them the target age group, the target biomarkers, the number of analyses or the LOQ of the analytical method employed. Hence, the following information should be clearly defined for each age group in a **study protocol** (see PARC general survey design):

- type of blood sample (whole blood, serum)
- information on blood collection tubes (volume, anticoagulant, etc.)
- fasting state or non-fasting state
- needed number of sample aliquots per sample type
- needed volume for each sample type (sufficient volume for the planned analysis)
- information that should be provided on the label
- storage temperature

Note: Fasting state vs. non fasting state for blood samples was discussed and agreed that it will not be feasible to align all the participating studies (PARC general survey design). Participants should not smoke prior to blood collection or do any sports.

Based to the most recent status of the discussion the following biomarkers will be analysed in blood samples:

- PFAS
- Metals (multi element analysis)

Best practice:

For the **analysis of trace elements**, special blood collection tubes should be used to minimise the background contamination, e.g., Vacuette® Trace Elements or BD Vacutainer® Trace Element tubes.

For the **analysis of PFAS** the use of **serum** as matrix is highly recommended according to the decision of PARCT4.1.2. In addition, for the analysis of PFAS in serum a **G-EQUAS** is available for the quality assurance of your analytical results.

To allow for the **analysis of additional biomarkers** of future interest, further aliquots per sample should be generated in addition to the aliquots for the analysis of the above-described biomarkers, depending on the consent and the ethics vote. Depending on the final number of biomarkers, aliquots of field blank samples should be generated as described in Part 1 to allow for the documentation and assessment of any background contamination.

Table 1: Overview – Aliquots to be collected

Age group	Target Biomarker	Sample Type	Obtained from blood collection tube	Sample Volume [mL]	Number of Aliquots	Aliquot Volume [mL]	Aliquots for confirmed biomarker	Aliquots for additional analysis
Teenagers	PFAS	Serum	9 mL** Serum without clotting agent	approx. 4.5 mL	5	approx. 0.8 mL	1	4
		Plasma	9 mL** K2 EDTA	approx. 4.5 mL	5	approx. 0.8 mL	1	4
		Field blank*			5		1	4
Adults	PFAS	Serum	9 mL** Serum without clotting agent	approx. 4.5 mL	5	approx. 0.8 mL	1	4
		Plasma	9 mL** K2 EDTA	approx. 4.5 mL	5	approx. 0.8 mL	1	4
	Metals	Whole blood	2.7 mL** K2 EDTA trace elements	approx. 2.7 mL	4	approx. 0.6 mL	1	3
		Field blank*			10		2	8
Children (optional)	PFAS	Serum	2.7 mL** Serum without clotting agent	approx. 1.6 mL	2	approx. 0.6 mL	1	1

	Plasma	2.7 mL** K2 EDTA	approx. 1.6 mL	2	approx. 0.6 mL	1	1
Metals	Whole blood	2.7 mL** K2 EDTA trace elements	2.7 mL	4	approx. 0.6 mL	1	3
	Field blank*			9		2	7

*Best Practice: From 10 % of the total number of participants for each sample type (see Part 1 of this Best Practice Document)

**Volume may vary with different manufacturers

2.2. Material needed for blood collection, processing and storage

2.2.1. Collection of blood samples

- Safety equipment (e.g., lab coat, powder-free disposable latex or similar gloves)
- Sampling instructions for the medical staff performing the phlebotomy with the telephone number of a contact person if medical staff need any additional information or support
- Sampling questionnaire
- Surface & hand disinfectant
- Blood collection tubes as defined in Table 1
- Tube racks
- Regular phlebotomy needle or butterfly needle set (please use materials from only one manufacturer and from the same lot for a coherent study)

Note: A butterfly set with silicon tube covered needles is recommended as it has a small, thin-walled needle that minimizes trauma to skin and vein and allows tubes to be changed without any movement of the needle in the vein. It provides the best possible protection against needle stick injuries.

- Tourniquet
- Alcohol prep pads or wipes for disinfection
- Gauze compresses & adhesive tape
- Scissors
- Pens
- Phlebotomy chair
- Biohazard waste containers
- Needle/sharps-proof dispose containers
- Field blanks (Blood collection tubes prepared according to the guideline in PART 1 – General Instructions)
- Labels with the assigned identification number (Participant-ID) suitable for temperatures down to -80 °C or -196 °C depending on the used freezing technology:
- labels for blood collection tubes
- labels for field blank aliquots (QA)

Note: All used material must be precisely labelled throughout sampling and handling stages to ensure adequate labelling. Pre-labelling of blood collection tubes and cryovials prior to the participant's visit is recommended. In studies requesting samples for metal testing, appropriate tubes should be used to avoid possible contaminations.

2.2.2. Processing and storage of blood samples

- Safety equipment according to biological safety level 2 (BSL2) containment (e.g., lab coat, powder-free disposable latex or similar gloves, safety glasses)
- Surface & hand disinfectant
- 10 x 2 mL pre-cleaned cryovials (polypropylene) per participant/field blank
- Cryovial racks
- Pens
- Biohazard waste containers

- Storage boxes (cryoboxes) for the sample and field blank aliquots
- -80 °C electrical freezers or liquid nitrogen storage infrastructure including respective equipment
- Pipettes/multipettes/dispensettes with corresponding tips (RNase-free, 1 mL)
- Centrifuge
- Labels with the assigned identification number suitable for temperatures down to -80 °C or -196 °C depending on the used freezing technology. These include:
 - labels for storage boxes
 - labels for aliquots of all samples including the field blank aliquots
 - labels for the field blanks (QA)

Note: All used material must be precisely labelled throughout sampling and handling stages to ensure adequate labelling. Pre-labelling of cryovials is recommended.

2.3. Collection of blood samples

Blood must be collected under constant medical supervision by staff well trained in phlebotomy knowing the special precautions related to the handling of biological material.

Please ensure that all necessary material for taking the blood is available (see page 3 and 4) and check if all tubes are properly labelled to ensure they are correctly coded (see PART 1 – General Instructions, page 5). Ideally, the blood collection should be done on the same day as the first morning urine sample and the interview takes place.

Best practice:

Blood samples are collected by arm vein puncture under sterile conditions and must be taken under medical supervision by trained medical staff. A detailed best practice guideline on drawing blood is provided by WHO (2010) [1] and should be followed (see References).

Before taking blood, participants must be informed about/on:

- goals of the study
- declaration of consent process
- sampling procedures and related risks
- pseudonymised data & sample processing
- data management, -processing & -storage and it must be ensured:
- that there is a declaration of consent from the participant.

Note: If sample processing does not take place on site directly after blood withdrawal, please provide contact information of the laboratory that is responsible for sampling processing in the information material for the fieldworkers.

2.3.1. Matrix-specific questionnaire accompanying the sampling of blood

Blood sampling should be accompanied by the collection of some basic information related to the blood sample and relevant questions that are necessary for the data interpretation. For a standardized data record, please use [Annex 4.1 or 4.3 - Blood sampling questionnaire for adults or teenagers](#).

2.3.2. Instruction for blood sampling

Blood should be collected and shipped to the laboratory, if necessary, between Monday and Thursday to avoid being in long transit for further processing, especially on weekend. **Please inform in advance by email the laboratories that are going to receive samples about the number, date of samples collection and date estimated for samples arrival.**

Please read carefully these instructions before taking the blood sample.

Best practice:

A detailed **sampling protocol** should be used to document the individual processing steps. The following table shows an example how such a protocol could be designed. Such protocols can be used to ensure whether all expected samples per participant have been collected or for which participant this is not the case or any other deviation. This protocol should also specify analytical priority in case the volume of the sample is not sufficient for all planned analyses.

Table 2: Sampling protocol – Example for samples from adults

Participant	1 x 9 mL K2 EDTA/trace elements for whole blood	1 x 9 mL Serum collection tube	1 x 9 mL K2 EDTA for plasma	Sampling conducted by	Date [dd.mm.yyyy]	notes/comments
	√ = present X = missing					
001	√	√			---'---'---	
002	√	X			---'---'---	
003	√	√			---'---'---	two punctures

Step-by-Step-Instruction:

1. Before starting blood collection, the working environment must be cleaned. Keep the blood handling area clean and free of dust.
2. Ensure that all necessary material for blood collection is available and use only the supplies provided for the study.
3. Prepare the blood collection tubes (K2 EDTA, serum tube without clotting agent) and label them with the code number and other relevant information. Please cross-check that the labels contain the correct participant-ID. Set up a tube rack with the set of blood collection tubes according to the order in which they are to be drawn.

Note:

Use closed evacuated collection/vacutainer systems to increase the safety of staff members and avoid further working steps and potential sources of contamination.

4. Prepare the volunteer for phlebotomy, following your normal protocol, using alcohol to disinfect the collection site. Do not use solvent or other disinfectant products.
5. Collect the amount of venous blood as defined per age group in Table 1
6. Fill completely the tubes to avoid the risk of haemolysis.

For whole blood (and plasma samples):

7. After removing the K2 EDTA blood collection tubes, invert them gently 8-10 times in order to mix the sample with the additive. After mixing, keep tube upright until further processing to avoid contact with stopper.
8. Process K2 EDTA blood samples as soon as possible but within 24 h. Keep the samples vertically in the fridge at +4-8 °C until their processing.
9. If transportation of samples to a laboratory for sample processing is required, blood samples should be transported in a cool box (+4-8°C) to the laboratory as fast as possible.
10. Record relevant details in the sampling protocol.

For serum samples (PFAS analysis):

11. After removing the serum tube (without clotting agent!) keep tubes upright and let them rest for at least 30 min but no longer than 60 min to allow a full clotting of the blood. Thereafter, process immediately according to the description on page 8.

12. Record relevant details in the sampling protocol.

2.4. Sample processing and storage

Best practice:

K2 EDTA blood samples (whole blood & plasma samples) should be processed on the same day as sample collection. If immediate processing after sampling of the K2 EDTA blood samples is not possible, store samples at 4-8°C until further processing. Ideally, samples should be processed and frozen immediately after sampling but within 24h after collection. Do not freeze blood samples before plasma processing since once samples are frozen plasma cannot be separated any more due to haemolysis.

Blood samples for serum separation should be processed immediately after the respective clotting time (30 - 60 min) ended. If serum samples cannot be frozen immediately after samples are processed, store serum samples at 4-8°C until freezing. Ideally, generated serum samples should be frozen immediately after samples are processed but within 24 hours. Do not freeze blood samples before serum processing since once samples are frozen serum cannot be separated any more due to haemolysis.

2.4.1. Blood sample processing

General remark:

Human blood samples, including whole blood, plasma, and serum are generally classified as potentially infectious. According to WHO guidelines, EU and national legislation, samples must be processed (including centrifugation and aliquoting) in a Biosafety Level 2 (BSL2) laboratory by trained personnel. Aliquot samples in a laminar-flow safety cabinet and wear personalized safety equipment.

Please ensure that all necessary material for sample processing is available (see page 4) and check if all cryovials are properly labelled (see PART 1 – General Instructions, page 5). Receipt of samples in the laboratory (date, time) and sample condition must be documented.

Best practice:

In order to avoid background contaminations resulting from the production process, **cryovials should be cleaned before use** according to a standardized protocol as described in Part 1 of this Best Practice Document.

2.4.2. Aliquoting

A detailed **process protocol** should be kept of the individual processing steps. The following table shows an example how such a protocol could be designed. Such protocols can be used to ensure whether all expected samples per participant have been processed and frozen or for which participant this is not the case. This protocol should also specify analytical priority in case the volume of the sample is not sufficient for all planned analyses.

Depending on the age group, generate the respective number of sample aliquots as described in **Table 1**.

Whole Blood: Open the blood collection tube in the laminar flow safety cabinet. Carefully transfer the whole blood into the cryovials. Use appropriate pipettes and sterile pipet tips and change the pipette tip after each sample. Place the cap on the vial tightly.

Serum: allow the sample to clot for at least 30 min but no more than 1 hour. Centrifuge the sample typically with 1000-1300 g [2] for 10 min at 4 °C to separate serum from the cellular fraction. Open the blood collection tube in the laminar-flow safety cabinet. Carefully transfer the serum into the cryovials avoiding transfer of the cellular components of blood. Use appropriate pipettes and sterile pipet tips and change the pipette tip after each sample. Close the cryovial tightly with the lid before removing it from the laminar-flow safety cabinet.

Table 3: Protocol on sample processing – Example

Participant	Arrival in the laboratory		Matrix	Aliquots for analysis	Aliquots for storage	Storage		Processed by	Notes
	Date [dd.mm.yyyy]	Time [hh:mm]				BW, BP, BS	number		
001	---	---				---	---		
002	---	---				---	---		
003	---	---				---	---		

3. Sample storage

Best practice:

Immediately after processing, the generated whole blood, serum and/or plasma aliquots should be stored at **-80 °C or lower** until further analysis or any other purpose (e.g., transfer to PARC partner or laboratory) (PART 1 – General Instructions).

4. Transport of samples to laboratories

A shipping date should be arranged between the sample collector and the laboratories for the planned analyses. When arrangements have been finalized, the addresses should be informed of the time and means of transportation.

All information related to a proper transport of the samples in human biomonitoring studies is given in the HBM4EU SOP “Strategy and SOPs for human sample exchange, including ethical demands”. This includes:

- Shipping Category B Biological Substances
- Pro-Forma Invoice
- Sample Transfer Protocol (Manifest)
- Data Transfer Template
- Material and Data Transfer Agreement

Documents can be downloaded from the [HBM4EU document library](#).

5. Tailored sampling protocol

Preparations for sampling cryovials

Sampling aliquot into **sterile cryovials** made of medical grade **polypropylene**, free of leachable, heavy metals, and DNase/RNase suitable for the used storage technology

Pre-treatment of cryovials for sampling and storage

→ Rinse all cryovials including the caps

→ Leave the cryovials to dry in their respective racks, upside down, in a safety cabinet (class 2)

→ Close the cryovials in the safety cabinet

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Preparations for sampling

Labelling

All **used material** must be **precisely labelled**: tubes, cryovials, freezer boxes...

Pre-labelling of collection tubes is recommended.

Minimum information on the cryovials that must be readable with electronic barcode readers

General survey	Country ID	Target group ID	Biological matrix ID	Participant ID	Aliquot ID
G	- XX	- X	- XX	- XXX	- XXX

2-digit abbreviation code according to ISO 3166

Children: **C**
Teenagers: **T**
Adults: **A**

Whole blood: **BW**
Plasma: **BP**
Serum: **BS**

3-digit number of participant in each country

Note

In studies where multiple aliquots are required for different analyses, a sample collection protocol should specify the exact procedure including the needed volume and the order in which the aliquots should be collected. This protocol should also specify analytical priority in case the volume of the sample is not sufficient for all planned analyses.

To allow for the analysis of additional biomarkers of future interest, further aliquots per sample should be generated in addition to the aliquots for the analysis of defined biomarkers depending on the consent and the ethics vote.

PARC

Blood sampling in children

For P4.1.1.3.b_Y4_PFASChildren_SpF project

PARC

Blood sampling in teenagers

PARC

Blood sampling in adults

PARC

Field blanks

From 10% of the total number of participants for each sample type

The number of aliquots of field blank samples should be at least equivalent to the total number of biomarkers analysed

PARC

Annex 3 – An illustration of best practices in phlebotomy (WHO, 2010) [1]

Best practice:

In contrast to the illustration shown below, use butterfly needle sets and suitable blood sampling tubes.

1. Assemble equipment and include needle and syringe or vacuum tube, depending on which is to be used.

2. Perform hand hygiene (if using soap and water, dry hands with single-use towels).

3. Identify and prepare the patient.

4. Select the site, preferably at the antecubital area (i.e. the bend of the elbow). Warming the arm with a hot pack, or hanging the hand down may make it easier to see the veins. Palpate the area to locate the anatomic landmarks. DO NOT touch the site once alcohol or other antiseptic has been applied.

5. Apply a tourniquet, about 4–5 finger widths above the selected venepuncture site.

6. Ask the patient to form a fist so that the veins are more prominent.

7. Put on well-fitting, non-sterile gloves.

8. Disinfect the site using 70% isopropyl alcohol for 30 seconds and allow to dry completely (30 seconds).

9. Anchor the vein by holding the patient's arm and placing a thumb **BELOW** the venepuncture site.

10. Enter the vein swiftly at a 30 degree angle.

11. Once sufficient blood has been collected, release the tourniquet **BEFORE** withdrawing the needle.

12. Withdraw the needle gently and then give the patient a clean gauze or dry cotton-wool ball to apply to the site with gentle pressure.

13. Discard the used needle and syringe or blood-sampling device into a puncture-resistant container.

14. Check the label and forms for accuracy.

15. Discard sharps and broken glass into the sharps container. Place items that can drip blood or body fluids into the infectious waste.

16. Remove gloves and place them in the general waste. Perform hand hygiene. If using soap and water, dry hands with single-use towels.

1. If the tube does not have a rubber stopper, press the plunger in slowly to reduce haemolysis (this is safer than removing the needle).

2. Place the stopper in the tube.

3. Following laboratory instructions, invert the sample gently to mix the additives with the blood before dispatch.

References

1. WHO, *WHO guidelines on drawing blood: best practices in phlebotomy*. 2010, World Health Organization. p. 109.
2. CDC, *Improving the Collection and Management of Human Samples Used for Measuring Environmental Chemicals and Nutrition Indicators*. 2018, U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.